

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE: AN EXPERIENCE FROM UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA TEACHING HOSPITAL ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The Study focuses on supply chain management and performance: An experience from university of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically the study aimed to pursue the following objectives: To determine the effect of strategic supplier partnership on goal attainment of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria, establish the nature of the relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria and ascertain the effect of quality of information sharing on employee performance of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria. The study had a population size of (1168) employees of University Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria. Instruments used for data collection were primary questionnaires and interview. The total number of 396 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, 354 copies were returned & used while 42 copies were not properly filled. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Three hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and simple linear regression tool. The findings indicated that A strategic supplier partnership positively and significantly affect goal attainment of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State ($r = 0.894$; $F = 1408.540$; $t = 37.531$; $P < 0.05$). There was a significant positive relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State ($r = 0.851$, $P < 0.05$). Quality of information sharing positively and significantly affect employee performance of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State ($r = 0.874$; $F = 171.811$; $t = 33.721$; $P < 0.05$). The study concluded that healthcare supply chain management involves obtaining resources, managing supplies, and delivering goods and services to providers and patients. The study recommends that Health institutions should always establish a long-term relationship between supplier and patients allowing for the free flow of feedback and ideas. Over time, this will create a more streamlined, effective supply chain that could have a positive impact on both costs, customer service, and goal attainment.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management; Strategic Supplier Partnership, Customer Relationship, Quality of Information Sharing, Goal Attainment and Customer Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

University of Nigeria teaching hospital is confronting diverse sorts of challenges in her exertion of competing in today's energetic worldwide markets. To stay competitive, University of Nigeria teaching hospital must recognize the significance of supply chain hones that progress not as it were her claim organizational execution but too arrange with their supply chain accomplices to make strides their joint execution. However, in spite of the critical progresses in investigate and hones, numerous organizations proceed to battle to get it the complex issues related with the facilitated arranging and supply exercises among the individuals of their supply systems (Lori et al., 2011)

Supply chain management (SCM) is one of the instruments that health institutions adopt to appreciate a competitive advantage over their competitors (Evans and Mawuko 2018). To endeavor in this worldwide setting companies, have to be create their competencies and, in competing with rivals', organizational capabilities (OC) stand as the center of competencies. As imperative is the illustrated positive link between organizational natural activities and client fulfillment, which this makes a difference gain market esteem, said Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006 (Wang, 2016).

It is vital that supply chains maximizes the by and large esteem created, since staying to a parcel of the chain not as it were makes no commitment to maximizing generally chain benefit but too decreases the full SC benefit (Heydari, et al., 2009). The leading supply chain hones are the activities that impact the complete supply chain, its parts or key forms. These practices are impacted by relevant variables such as sort of industry, firm measure in position within the supply chain, sort and length of supply chain (Li et al., 2006).

SCM has been ended up a noteworthy part and recognized as one of basic figure for execution of trade and trade organization competitive advantage (Gunasekaran, Patel, & McGaughey, 2004; Larson, and Kulchitsky, 1998) .A business competitive environment required the commerce organizations producing high quality items and services that are required by target clients (Fawcett, & Magnan, 2001; Lin, ., Chow, , Madu, , Kuei, & Yu, 2005).

Healthcare costs are persistently spiraling up and clinics are confronting soak competition to supply tall quality administrations (Dobrzykowski, 2012; HFMA, 2012:2). As such, supply chain performance and esteem creation exercises with upstream and downstream on-screen characters have expanded in significance for healthcare suppliers (Pralhalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). The impacts of supply chain administration on health care quality need to do with quality from a regulatory point of see, therapeutic benefit quality which can be measured from a proficient therapeutic viewpoint, or from the beneficiary of such administrations, the quiet. The regulatory point of view is the center of this study. The quality of wellbeing care administrations rendered from an authoritative viewpoint essentially should do with utilizing the available assets and the ability to draw in unused ones to cover the specified needs of uncommon benefit, which gives the correct benefit at the proper time at a sensible fetched.

The healthcare supply chain is composed of three major players at different stages, specifically, makers, purchasers, and healthcare suppliers. Producers incorporate pharmaceutical companies, medical-surgical items companies, gadget producers, and producers of capital hardware and data frameworks. Purchasers incorporate assembled obtaining organizations (GPOs), pharmaceutical wholesalers, medical-surgical wholesalers, free contracted wholesalers, and item agents from producers. Suppliers incorporate healing centers, frameworks of healing centers, coordinates conveyance systems (IDNs), and interchange location offices (Toba, Tomasini, & Yang,, 2008). Inside healthcare sectors, quality management activities have been raised and healing center on how quality care can be conveyed to impact results with regard to hospital performance and persistent fulfillment (Jiang, Friedman & Started 2006). In later a long time SCM has drawn critical consideration within the healthcare industry since SCM appears a noteworthy impact on hospital performance in terms of lessening squandering, avoiding therapeutic mistakes, progressing quality of care and services and expanding operational efficiencies. (Bayrnes, 2004; Schneller & Smeltzer, 2006; Kowalski, 2009; Sinha, & Kohnke, 2009)

Statement of the Problem

Supply chain administration practice is anticipated to extend an organization's showcase share, return on venture and make strides by and large competitive position. For illustration, vital provider association has been detailed to surrender organization-specific benefits in terms of money related performance. Progressed plan and calculated joins with providers are related to better-performing plants. Client connection hones have too been appeared to lead to noteworthy enhancement in organizational performance. The higher level of data sharing is related with the lower add up to taken a toll, the higher-order fulfillment rate and the shorter-order cycle time. In spite of of the awesome part of supply chain administration practice,, it is evidenced that at University Teaching Hospital Enugu Nigeria are not implemented effective supply chain management which have not improved on its competitive advantage and its performance thus the study seeks to investigate supply chain management and performance: An experience from university of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives were to

- 1) To determine the effect of strategic supplier partnership on goal attainment of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria
- 2) To establish the nature of the relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction
- 3) To ascertain the effect of quality of information sharing on employee performance

Research Hypotheses

These hypotheses were proposed for the study

- 1) A strategic supplier partnership does not affect goal attainment of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria
- 2) There is no relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction
- 3) Quality of information sharing does not affect employee performance

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review: Supply Chain Management

Christopher (2005) defined SCM as “the administration of upstream and downstream connections with providers and clients to provide prevalent client esteem at less fetched to the supply chain as a whole.” Stadtler (2008) Supply chain management is “the errand of joining organizational units along a supply chain and planning fabric, data and monetary streams in arrange to fulfill (extreme) client requests with the point of moving forward the competitiveness of a supply chain as a whole.” Simchi-Levi et al. (2003) considered SCM as “a set of approaches utilized to proficiently coordinated providers, producers, distribution centers, and stores, so that stock is delivered and dispersed at the proper amounts, to the correct locations, and at the correct time, in arrange to play down framework wide costs whereas fulfilling benefit level requirements.”

Strategic Supplier Partnership and Goal Attainment

This is defined as the long-term relationship between the organization and its providers. It is outlined to use the vital and operational capabilities of person partaking organizations to assist them accomplish critical continuous benefits (Tan KC, et al., 2005). A key organization emphasizes coordinate, long-term affiliation and empowers common arranging and issue fathoming endeavors). Such strategic partnerships are entered into to advance shared benefits among the parties and progressing interest in one or more key vital regions such as innovation, items, and markets (Croorn et al (1998). Strategic partnerships with providers empower organizations to work more viably with a couple of vital providers who are willing to share duty for the victory of the items. Suppliers participating early within the item plan prepare can offer more cost-effective design choices, help select the most excellent components and innovations, and offer assistance in plan appraisal (Tan KC, et al 2002). Objective setting is vital for well-being, since individuals frequently set objectives as points of reference in endeavors to fulfill desire and life plans. Diener (1984) contends that having objectives that are vital (targets that are actually wanted and esteemed) is central to someone’s satisfaction with life. The objectives advise us approximately what we have to be do; they organize our endeavors, and decide our activities. As such, objectives donate meaning and structure to our lives. Observational discoveries bolster this idea, appearing that, in common, individuals who seek after esteemed objectives report higher well-being than those who are lost this sort of goal-directedness (Emmons, 1986; Freund & Baltes, 2002).

Customer Relationship and Organizational Performance

This comprises any practices that are utilized for the reason of overseeing client complaints, building long-term connections with clients, and progressing client satisfaction (Tan KC, et al., 2002). Cigolini R, et al 2004) considers client relationship administration as a vital component of supply chain administration practices. As pointed out by Day (Tan KC, et al 2002), committed connections are the foremost maintainable advantage since of their inalienable obstructions to competition. The development of mass customization and personalized benefit is driving to a time in which relationship administration with customers is getting to be significant for corporate survival (Tan KC, et al., 2006). Good connections with supply chain individuals, counting clients, are required for fruitful execution of supply chain management programs (Moberg CR et al., 2002). Close customer relationship permits an organization to distinguish its item from competitors, maintain client dependability, and significantly expand the esteem it gives to its customers (Tan KC, et al., 2002).

Concurring to Ibojo and Asabi (2015), companies point to fulfill their clients as client satisfaction moreover serves as an establishment upon which other destinations can be built upon and accomplished. They too included that it reflected the organization's accomplishments. Safi (2017), clarified that a fulfilled client speaks to fundamental data to different partners just like the company administration, arrangement creators, rivals and other clients - one of the ways that the companies can too accomplish client fulfillment and devotion is by guaranteeing that the benefit that they provide is of full quality. Clients need to be treated in such a way that they will feel upbeat to portion with their cash and this will their satisfaction. Neighborly staff will make them feel comfortable and give a sense of belonging. However, there's truly got to be mindful when it comes to benefit quality because it has been found that when a client experiences awful benefit they would likely tell numerous people

Quality of information sharing and Employee performance

Quality of information sharing: This incorporates such angles as the exactness, convenience, adequacy, and validity of data traded (Tan KC, et al., 2002). Whereas data sharing is critical, the importance of its impact on supply chain management depends on what data is shared, when and how it is shared, and with whom (Tan KC et al., 2002). Writing is loaded with case of the broken impacts of inaccurate/delayed data, as data moves along the supply chain. Disparate interface and astute behavior of supply chain accomplices, and instructive asymmetries over supply chain influence the quality of data Feldmann & Muller (2003). It has been recommended that organizations will purposely mutilate data that can possibly reach not as it were their competitors, but too their claim providers and clients (Croorn et al., 1998). It shows up that there's a built in hesitance inside organizations to deliver absent more than negligible data since data divulgence is seen as a misfortune of control. Given these inclinations, guaranteeing the quality of the shared data gets to be a basic angle of compelling supply chain administration Feldmann & Muller (2003). Organizations got to see their data as a key resource and guarantee that it streams with least delay and twisting. "Employee performance" implies an individual's

work accomplishment after applying required exertion on the work which is related through getting an important work, locked in profile, and compassionate colleagues/employers around (Karakas, 2010) the performance driven objective is anticipated to be adjusted with the organizational approaches

Supply Chain Management and Organization Performance:

Organizational performance alludes to how well an organization accomplishes its market-oriented objectives as well as its budgetary objectives. The short-term targets of supply chain management are fundamentally to extend efficiency and decrease stock and cycle time, while long-term destinations are to extend advertise share and benefits for all individuals of the supply chain. Kyeremeh and Mawuko (2018) conducted a study on Supply Chain Management and Organization Performance: An Esteem Creation Point of view and the result uncovered in spite of the fact that supply chain management hones have a few level that affect supply chain execution. Inda, Shouvik and, Ali (2020) did a study on Supply Chain management Practices and Organizational Performance: An Examination from Benefit Industry, key supply chain organization and organizational performance was positive related to performance. (2) There's critical effect of client relationship on organizational performance. Hassana and Cross (2020) did a study on Impact of Supplier Development on Operational Performance of Fabricating Firms in Nigeria and the comes about demonstrate found-out that provider specialized bolster has factually critical impact on competitive advantage at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc., early provider inclusion has measurably critical impact on taken a toll effectiveness at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc., provider review has factually critical impact on operational effectiveness at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc. and provider certification has factually noteworthy impact on client benefit conveyance at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc. Suhong, Bhanu, Ragu-Nathanb, and. Subba (2004) did a study on the effect of supply chain administration practices on competitive advantage and organizational performance; the result indicates that higher levels of SCM hone can lead to improved competitive advantage and moved forward organizational execution. Makena and Mike (2014) conducted a study on Effect of Supply Chain Administration Practices on Organizational Execution: A Case Consider of Haco Businesses Restricted (Kenya). Fundamental discoveries of the think about uncovered that there's a tall level of viable execution of SCM hones in Haco Industries ltd which they all had a positive impact on organization's execution that's they moved forward the organization's execution in terms of bringing down its operational costs, lessening of lead time, tall customer service levels, item quality, quick reaction to changes within the showcase and growing its advertise share and sales. A combination of all the four hones considered had a more grounded impact

Systems Theory

Von Bertalanffy (1956) defines a framework as a complex of collaboration components. Von Bertalanffy cultivates frameworks considering in all disciplines in arrange to discover common standards substantial to all frameworks. It presents "system" as a modern logical worldview differentiating the explanatory, mechanical worldview; characterizing classical science (von Bertalanffy, 1956). A principal idea of general frameworks hypothesis is its

center on intuition. The center in connections lead to sustain that the behavior of a single independent component is distinctive from its behavior when the component is interatomic with other components. Another center principle is the refinement between open, closed and confined frameworks. In open systems there are trades of vitality, matter, individuals, and data with the outside environment. In closed systems there are no trades of data and matter, fair trades of vitality. In separated framework, there's no trade of components. Building on common frameworks hypothesis numerous approaches developed. Among others there are open framework hypothesis, reasonable framework show and reasonable framework approach. Open framework hypothesis (OST) looks at the connections between the organizations and the environment in which they are included. This center reflects on organizations' capacity to adjust to changes in natural conditions (with or without the requirements for data handling) (Boulding, 1956; Katz and Kahn, 1978). This hypothesis accept that substances able of handling data almost claim particular environment appear more adjustment aptitudes to shifts in relevant conditions. In SCM setting frameworks theory brings together different components of a complex supply chain (that's the human. capital. data. materials and financial resources etc.) to make a subs) stem " hich is at that point portion of a bigger framework of supply chains or organize. The hypothesis contends organization's that for an all-encompassing point of view systems theory must be utilized to get it the inside and outside l~tctors that shape an organisation's supply chain performance.

Empirical Review

Lee, (2021) (2021) did a study on the effect of supply chain management strategy on operational and Financial Performance .This study ~~aims to identify~~ the effects of supply chain management (SCM) on the operational performance of SMEs in Korea, specifically considering organizational competencies. To achieve this, an empirical survey was conducted on 300 Korean manufacturing SMEs that had introduced SCM strategies. The relationships between the variables were analyzed through structural equation modeling. The result shows that specific SCM strategies and organizational competencies had a significant effect on overall business performance. Furthermore, the SCM strategies had a significant effect on SME organizational competencies. Additionally, study analyzed the mediating effect of organizational competencies on the effect of SCM strategy on overall business performance. The study found that organizational competence mediated the effect of SCM strategy on operational performance, but not on financial performance. The study shows that introducing SCM strategies directly improves business performance and is closely related to competencies such as research and development, technology commercialization, production capability, and marketing capabilities. Consequently, a combination of SCM strategies and organizational competencies can generate sustainable overall business performance among SME

Aswini Priya andVelmurugan (2019) conducted a study on the effect of supply chain Management Practices on Organizational Performance: An Experimental Approach.the fundamental reason of this study is to decide the impact of supply chain management practices (i.e., key provider organization, quality of data sharing, client relationship, level of data sharing, delay, and hazard and compensate sharing on organizational execution,

that's, promoting execution and money related execution). The instrument was received, and managed to 115 target respondents from 6 organizations in Chennai. A substantial of 100 sample was taken for advance investigation, and multiple regression was utilized to decide the reason. The discoveries demonstrated that supply chain administration practices (i.e., vital provider association, client relationship, level of data sharing, quality of data sharing, delay, and chance and remunerate sharing) have noteworthy and positive effect on organizational performance (i.e., promoting and money related performance).

Carren, Esther and Noor (2020) Strategic supplier relationship on performance of declined frameworks of government in Kenya. The reason for this study was to examine the impact of strategic supplier relationship on the performance of the degenerated framework of government in Kenya, the consider embraced a cross-sectional overview plan utilizing both quantitative and subjective approaches. The target population for this study was all representatives working in back and obtainment offices in 10 provinces specifically; Garissa, Kisii, Nyamira, Narok, Marsabit, Murang' a Bomet, Nairobi, Kiambu and Homa Bay. Our study utilized stratified random inspection to choose 186 respondents from back and acquirement office. Information was collected by utilizing surveys Descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized helped by Factual Bundles for Social Sciences adaptation 24 to compute rates of respondents' answers. Speculation testing was carried utilizing different relapse investigation and standard F tests. They study found that there is a positive and significant relationship between strategic supplier relationships and the performance of degenerated frameworks of government. We prescribe that degenerated frameworks of government ought to conduct together item improvement with providers and include providers straightforwardly or by implication in their key plans. Suppliers' inclusion would back the company's improvement development and capabilities in this way expanding the benefits seen by the company's clients.

Onyango et.al (2015) centered on the impact of strategic supplier relationship management on inside operational performance of fabricating firms, centering on business-supplier communication and business-supplier joint choice making. The discoveries set up that there's a positive noteworthy relationship between buyer- provider joint choices, provider communication management and inside operational performance of fabricating firms in Kenya.

This propose that firms with well-overseenoverseen provider communication frameworks, execute buyer provider joint choices have delighted in prevalent client benefit levels and advancement in inner operational performance. Upgraded supplier relations progress supplier performance which result in high levels of inside operations performance. Moreover, successful communication framework improves data stream between the firm and its suppliers subsequently coming about in tall level of operational performance. Subsequently, it's significant for organizations to move forward on their communication channels, through a devoted data framework that encourage genuine time communication particularly with their key provider and at long last to enter into long term key relationship with their suppliers.

Miranti, Arik, and Muhammad (2019) conducted to examine the impact of vital provider organizations on the supply chain integration, supply chain performance and agriculturists performance. This investigate is an informative inquire about with a quantitative approach. The information was collected utilizing surveys. The inspecting strategy was multistage relative arbitrary examining of 200 respondents. Information investigation in this consider utilized way examination strategy with offer assistance by SPSS. The comes about of this think about demonstrate that key provider organizations have no noteworthy impact on supply chain integration, supply chain performance and farmers performance. The supply chain integration incorporates a noteworthy positive impact toward supply chain performance and farmers execution. Whereas the supply chain performance contains a noteworthy positive impact toward farmers performance

Muhammad, Naveed Haider and Alamdar (2015) did a study on impact of customer relationship administration capabilities on organizational execution; Directing Part of Competition Escalated. Populace of this investigation was telecom division in Pakistan. Anticipated test measure was 300 representatives from telecom organizations. They was be managed through embrace survey counting Client relationship management capability (Client Interaction administration capability and client relationship updating capability), organizational performance and competition escalated.

Different calculated relapse investigation tests was utilized for advance examination. The current consideration was empower companies to form a long term and solid relationship with their clients. This investigation would empower organizations to get it and utilize their capabilities superior to what was conceivable sometime recently

Leslie , Naa, and Afako (2019)conducted a consider on Consumer Relationship Management and Its Impact On Organizational Performance Inside the Media transmission Industry of Ghana ,The study was-quantitative in nature and a direct relapse demonstrate was utilized to survey the impact CRM has on Organizational Performance. A noteworthy finding made from the study was that CRM on the off chance that well implemented includes a positive impact on the performance of an organization. An imperative suggestion made is, businesses ought to make strides on their CRM practice since it moves forward their Organizational performance.

Jalal (2022) did a study on an Investigation of the Impact of Customer Relationship Management on Organizational Performance within the Managing an account Division. The most objective of the study was to test the linkages among client relationship management (CRM) practices and organizational performance in Palestinian managing an account division.

The study was based on web study which was planned for gathering the information from a few representatives who is keeping their moneyin this division. 223 reactions were considered substantial for information examination utilizing SPSS and fractional slightest square approach (PLS-SEM). By and large, the discoveries confirmed that client introduction and CRM organization have critical positive impacts on organizational performance. The results moreover affirmed that CRM innovation and information management play a significant parts in influencing organizational performance.

Fahmi and Ahmad (2018) examined the relationship between CRM organization variables (i.e. top administration support, client orientation, training orientation) and organization performance of medium ventures in Indonesia. These medium ventures are worked in media transmission industry. This can be a quantitative study employing a study strategy of self-administered survey. The stratified testing strategy is chosen and 82 respondents are the workers from three ventures.

Information collected was analyzed utilizing relationship and relapse investigation to test the show and clarify relationship between factors. The results of this study found that the organization components of CRM (i.e. top management support, client orientation, preparing orientation) have a positive and noteworthy affect on organization performance. CRM could be a potential framework that has tremendous and positive affect to the clients and trade performance which recommended to be embraced widely by the medium endeavors of media transmission industry in Indonesia.

Imam and Amrik (2013) did a study on the impact of information sharing in supply chains on authoritative performance: an experimental ponder. This think about conceptualises and surveys a few components that impact the degree of information sharing in supply chains, to be specific coordinates data innovations, inside integration, data quality and costs–benefits sharing.

The relationship between the degree of information sharing and authoritative performance is at that point tried. Information from 150 fabricating companies were collected and proposed connections are inspected utilizing auxiliary condition displaying. The comes about appear that coordinates data innovations and data quality have positive impact on the escalated of data sharing. In any case, inside integration and costs–benefits sharing don't relate to the escalated of data sharing. This consider finds that data sharing does not specifically relate to hierarchical performance, its relationship is intervened by collaboration

Roaimah, Ramayah, May-Chuin and Rusinah(2020) did a study on Information sharing, data quality and utilization of data innovation (IT) instruments in Malaysian organizations ,This think about looks at the level of information sharing, data quality and utilization of data innovation (IT) devices among fabricating companies found within the Northern locale of Malaysia.

A add up to of 250 surveys coordinated to the operations and procurement/purchasing directors were disseminated through electronic mail. The comes about show that fabricating firms recognized the importance of data sharing, data quality and IT instruments utilization within the setting of supply chain administration.

The utilization of IT apparatuses is between direct to tall. Generally, the comes about give bits of knowledge into the sorts of data shared between producers and providers, the viewpoints of data quality emphasized as well as the IT devices utilized by the fabricating firms

Christine and Yusuf (2019) inspected the impact of data sharing on supply chain execution of tourism industry in Kakamega District. The consider was guided in deciding the impact of collaboration and organizing on supply chain execution of tourism industry in Western Locale. An illustrative overview plan was utilized. The target populace comprised of 459 workers working in 4 authorized visit companies and 5 authorized inns in Kakamega Province (Tourism Administrative Specialist, Western Locale, 2016). Survey was utilized as inquire about instrument.

The analyst found out that collaboration impacts supply chain execution. It was placated that organizing impacts supply chain execution. The consider concluded that data sharing impacts supply chain execution of tourism industry in Kakamega District. The investigate prescribed that the supply chain division ought to receive viable organizing programs in arrange to upgrade client fulfillment and supply chain productivity thus expanding get to of data almost the providers and the administration of the inns and visit companies ought to give different collaboration programs in arrange to extend suppliers to collaborating with other providers so as to supply data for the lodgings and visit companies around their clients.

METHOD AND MATERIALS

The study was carried out using a survey design. Primary data was obtained through the use of interviews, questionnaires, and observations while Secondary data were obtained through books, journals, and the internet. The population of the study was 1168 drawn from employees of a University Nigeria teaching hospital in Enugu State Nigeria. A sample size of 396 was determined from the population using Cochran's sample size determination method.

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire structured in 5- point Likert scale and validated with content face validity. The reliability test was done using the test-retest method. The result gave a reliability coefficient of 0.877, indicating a high internal consistency of the items. Three hundred and ninety-six (396) copies of the questionnaire were distributed and three hundred and fifty four (354) copies were returned while forty two copies (42) were not returned.

The three hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Simple linear regression was used to test hypotheses one, and three while hypothesis two was tested using the Pears product-moment correlation coefficient. A computer-aided Microsoft special package for social science (SPSS Version 20.00) was used to aid analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained from the field were presented and analyzed with descriptive statistics to provide answers to the research questions while the corresponding hypotheses were tested with Pearson's product-moment correlation efficient and simple linear regression at a 0 .05 alpha level

Table 1: Responses on Strategic Supplier Partnership and Goal Attainment

S/N	Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
	Strategic Supplier Partnership						
1	Strategic supplier partnerships ensure that there is cost-effectiveness in service delivery	203 (57.34%)	134 (37.85%)	5 (1.41%)	6 (1.70%)	6 (1.70%)	354
2	Effective practice of strategic supplier partnership sure smooth running of activities in technology and products	160 (45.20%)	175 (49.44%)	4 (1.13%)	8 (2.26%)	7 (1.98)	354
3	Hospitals can be ensured with mutual planning and problem-solving efforts through strategic supplier partnership	59 (16.67%)	104 (29.38%)	34 (9.60%)	68 (19.21%)	89 (25.14%)	354
	Goal Attainment						
4	Health institutions can achieve a goal set out through the effective application of strategic partnership	230 (64.97%)	103 (29.10%)	6 (1.70%)	6 (1.70%)	9 (2.54%)	354
5	Goal attainment in my hospital directs and controls all activities in our hospital	140 (39.55)	187 (52.83)	8 (2.26)	12 (3.39)	7 (1.98)	354
6	Being the best hospital is a benchmark is a determinant for effective result	211 (59.61%)	130 (36.72%)	5 (1.41%)	4 (1.13%)	4 (1.13%)	354

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

Item 1 of Table 1 Indicates that 203(57.34%) of the respondents strongly agreed Strategic supplier partnership ensures that there is cost-effectiveness in service delivery, 134(37.85%) agreed, 5(1.41%) were undecided, 6(1.70%) disagreed while 6(1.70) strongly disagreed to the statement. The above result indicates that a Strategic supplier partnership ensures that there is cost-effectiveness in service delivery

Item 2 of table 1 states that Effective practice of strategic supplier partnership sure smooth running of activities in technology and products, 160 (45.20%) strongly agreed with the statement, 175(49.44%) agreed, 4(1.13%) were undecided,8(2.26) disagreed while 7(1.98%) strongly disagreed to the statement. Thus, the result reveals that effective practice of strategic supplier partnership sure smooth running of activities in technology and products

Item 3 of Table shows that 59(16.67%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Hospitals can be ensured with mutual planning and problem-solving effort through strategic supplier partnership, 104(29.38%) agreed, 34(9.60%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 68(19.21%) disagreed to the statement while 89 (25.14%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The above finding reveal that Hospitals

can be ensure with mutual planning and problem solving effort through strategic supplier partnership

Item 4 of table 1 indicates that 230(64.97%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Health institutions can achieve goal set out through effective application of strategic partnership, 103 (29.10%) agreed, 6(1.70%) were undecided, 6(1.70) of the respondents disagree while 9(2.54%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result indicates that Health institutions can achieve goal set out through effective application of strategic partnership

Item 5 of table 1 Indicates that 140(39.55%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Goal attainment in my hospital direct and control all activates in our hospital, 187(52.83%) agreed, 8(2.26%) were undecided, 12(3.39%) disagreed while 7(1.98) strongly disagreed to the statement. Thus the result shows that Goal attainment in my hospital direct and control all activates in our hospital t. Item 6 of table 1 Indicates that 211(59.61%) of the respondents strongly agreed to be among the best hospital is a benchmark is a determinant for effective results 130(36.72%) agreed, 5(1.41%) were undecided, 4(1.13%) disagreed while 4(1.13) strongly disagreed to the statement. Thus the result shows that to being among the best hospital is a benchmark is a determinant for effective result

Ho¹: A strategic supplier partnership does not affect goal attainment

Table 1a: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.894 ^a	.800	.799	.35269	.169
a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Supplier Partnership					
b. Dependent Variable: Goal attainment					

Table 1b: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	175.211	1	175.211	1408.540	.000 ^b
	Residual	43.786	352	.124		
	Total	218.997	353			
a. Dependent Variable: Goal attainment						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Supplier Partnership						

Table 1c: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.269	.042		6.460	.000
	Strategic Supplier Partnership	.921	.025	.894	37.531	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Goal attainment						

- R = 0.894
- R² = 0.800
- F = 1408.540
- T = 37.531
- DW = 0.169

Interpretation:

The regression sum of squares (175.211) is greater than the residual sum of squares (43.786), which indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.894, indicates that there is positive relationship between strategic supplier partnership and goal attainment. R square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 80.0% of the goal attainment is explained by the model. With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .35269. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.169, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation. The strategic supplier partnership coefficient of 0.894 indicates a positive strategic supplier partnership and goal attainment, which is statistically significant (with $t = 37.531$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus A strategic supplier partnership positively and significantly affect goal attainment

Table 2: Responses on Customer Relationship and Customer Satisfaction

	Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
7	My hospital manage customer complaints effectively	207 (58.47)	122 (34.46)	7 (1.98)	10 (2.83)	8 (2.26)	354
8	Building long term relationships with customers boost my hospital image	240 (67.80)	103 (29.10)	3 (0.85)	5 (1.41)	3 (0.85)	354
9	Our customer are satisfy with the service render by my hospital	223 (62.99%)	115 (32.49%)	4 (1.13%)	7 (1.98%)	5 (1.41%)	354
	Customer Satisfaction						
10	Quality of our service rendered by hospital increase our productivity	198 (55.93%)	140 (39.54%)	3 (0.85%)	6 (1.70%)	7 (1.98%)	354
11	My hospital patients are satisfy due to quality services render by my hospital	209 (59.04%)	130 (36.72%)	4 (1.13%)	7 (1.98%)	4 (1.13%)	354
12	Effective customer relationship boost hospital performance	239 (67.51)	98 (27.68)	7 (1.98%)	4 (1.13%)	6 (1.70%)	354

Source: Fieldwork 2022

Item 7 of table 2 states that my hospital manage customer complaints effectively, 207 (58.47%) strongly agreed with the statement, 122(34.46%) agreed, 7(1.98%) were undecided, 10 (2.83) disagreed while 8(2.26%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result indicate my hospital manage customer complaints effectively

Item 8 of table 2 shows that 204(67.80%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Building long term relationships with customers boost my hospital image, 103(29.10%) agreed, 3(0.89%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 5(1.41%) disagreed to the statement while 3 (0.85%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. Thus the study reveals that building long term relationships with customers boost my hospital image of customers, because they are directly involved with customers

Item 9 of table 2 shows that 223(62.99%) of the respondents strongly agreed that our customer are satisfy with the service render by my hospital, 115(32.49%) agreed, 4(1.13%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 7(1.98%) disagreed to the statement while 5 (1.41%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The finding shows that our customer are satisfy with the service render by my hospital

Item 10 of table 2 shows that 198(55.93%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Quality of our service rendered by hospital increase our productivity, 140(39.54%) agreed, 3(0.85%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 6(1.70%) disagreed to the statement while 7 (1.98%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The result indicates Quality of our service rendered by hospital increase our productivity

Item 11 of table 2 shows that 209(59.04%) of the respondents strongly agreed that my hospital patients are satisfy due to quality services render by my hospital, 130(36.72%) agreed, 4(1.13%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 7(1.98%) disagreed to the statement while 4 (1.13%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The result reveal that my hospital patients are satisfy due to quality services render by my hospital

Item 12 of table 2 shows that 239(67.51%) of the respondents strongly agreed that effective customer relationship boost hospital performance, 98(27.68%) agreed, 7(1.98%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 4(1.13%) disagreed to the statement while 6 (1.70%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The result reveal that effective customer relationship boost hospital performance

Ho²: There is no relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction

Table 2a: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Customer Relationship	1.5678	.81570	354
Customer Satisfaction	1.3842	.66425	354

Table 2b: Correlations

		Customer Relationship	Customer Satisfaction
Customer Relationship	Pearson Correlation	1	.851**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	354	354
Customer Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.851**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table (2a) shows the descriptive statistics of the customer relationship and customer satisfaction with a mean response of 1.5678 and std. deviation of .81570 for customer relationship and a mean response of 1.3842 and std. deviation of .66425 for customer satisfaction and number of respondents (354). By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table (2b) is the Pearson correlation coefficient for customer relationship and customer satisfaction. The correlation coefficient shows 0.851. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction ($r = .851$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 352 degrees of freedom ($df. = n-2$) at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .815, p < .05$). However, since the computed $r = .815$, is greater than the table value of $.195$ we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction ($r = .851, P < .05$).

Table 3: Responses on Quality of information sharing and employee performance

S/N	Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
	Quality of information sharing						
13	My hospital accuracy information save patients life	222 (62.71)	109 (30.79)	5 (1.41)	10 (2.83)	8 (2.26)	354
14	Credibility of information exchange from our supplier ensure hospital not to run out from drugs	275 (77.68)	62 (17.51)	6 (1.70)	5 (1.41)	6 (1.70)	354

15	Timeliness information can keep our hospital ahead ensuring that patients are well treated	150 (42.37)	188 (53.11)	7 (1.98)	4 (1.13)	5 (1.41)	354
	Employee performance						
16	Employees are assets that can ensure that goal are achieved	65 (18.36)	275 (77.68)	4 (1.13)	4 (1.13)	6 (1.70)	354
17	Doctors and nurses ensure that patients are treated on time	200 (56.50)	134 (37.85)	4 (1.13)	10 (2.83)	6 (1.70)	354
18	Nurses ensure that patients get their injections and drugs when due	210 (59.32)	126 (35.59)	5 (1.41)	8 (2.26)	5 (1.41)	354

Source: Filed work 2022

Item 13 of table 3 Indicates that 222(62.71%) of the respondents strongly agreed that my hospital accuracy information save patients life. 109(30.79%) agreed, 5(1.41%) were undecided, 10(2.83%) disagreed while 8(2.26) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result indicates that my hospital accuracy information save patients life

Item 14 of table 3 states that Credibility of information exchange from our supplier ensure hospital not to run out of drugs, 275 (77.68%) strongly agreed with the statement, 62(17.51%) agreed, 6(1.70%) were undecided, 5 (1.41%) disagreed while 6(1.70%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The finding indicates that Credibility of information exchange from our supplier ensure hospital not to run out of drugs

Item 15 of table 3 shows that 150(42.37%) of the respondents strongly agreed that timeliness information can keep our hospital ahead ensuring that patients are well treated 188(53.11%) agreed, 7(1.98%) of the respondents were indifference about the statement, 4(1.13%) disagreed to the statement while 5 (1.41%) of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The finding shows that Timeliness information can keep our hospital ahead ensuring that patients are well treated

Item 16 of table 3 indicates that 65(18.36%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Nurses ensure that patients get their injection and drugs at when due, 275 (77.68%) agreed, 4 (1.13%) were undecided, 4(1.13) of the respondents disagree while 5(1.41%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result shows that Nurses ensure that patients get their injections and drugs at when due

Item 17 of table 3 indicates that 200(56.50%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Doctors and nurses ensure that patients are treated on time, 134 (37.85%) agreed, 4 (1.13%) were undecided, 10(2.83) of respondents disagree while 6(1.70%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result shows that Doctors and nurses ensure that patients are treated on time

Item 18 of Table 3 indicates that 210(59.32%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Nurses ensure that patients get their injections and drugs when due, 126 (39.59%) agreed, 5 (1.41%) were undecided, 8(2.26) of the respondents disagree while 5(1.41%) strongly disagreed to the statement. The result shows that Nurses ensure that patients get their injections and drugs when due

Ho³: Quality of information sharing does not affect employee performance

Table 3a: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.874 ^a	.764	.763	.38871	.171
a. Predictors: (Constant), Quality of information sharing					
b. Dependent Variable: Employee performance					

Table 3b ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	171.811	1	171.811	1137.088	.000 ^p
	Residual	53.186	352	.151		
	Total	224.997	353			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Quality of information sharing						

Table 3c Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.025	.044		1.577	.300
	Quality of information sharing	.879	.026	.874	33.721	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance						

R = 0.874

R² = 0.764

F = 171.811

T = 33.721

DW = 0.171

Interpretation:

The regression sum of squares (171.811) is greater than the residual sum of squares (53.186), which indicates that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistics (0.000) is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance.

R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.874, indicates that there is positive relationship between Quality of information sharing and Employee performance. R square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 76.4% of the employee performance is explained by the model.

With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .38871. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.171, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation.

The Quality of information sharing coefficient of 0.874 indicates a positive Quality of information sharing and employee performance, which is statistically significant (with $t = 33.721$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus Quality of information sharing positively and significantly affect employee performance

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of this study include the following

- 1) A strategic supplier partnership positively and significantly affect goal attainment of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = 0.894$; $F = 1408.540$; $t = 37.531$; $P < 0.05$)
- 2) There is a significant positive relationship between customer relationship and customer satisfaction of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .851$, $P < .05$).
- 3) Quality of information sharing positively and significantly affect employee performance of University of Nigeria teaching hospital Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = 0.874$; $F = 171.811$; $t = 33.721$; $P < 0.05$)

Conclusion

Healthcare supply chain management, according to the report, entails procuring resources, managing supplies, and delivering goods and services to providers and patients.

Physical commodities and information concerning medical products and services are frequently passed through a variety of independent parties, such as manufacturers, insurance companies, hospitals, providers, and group purchasing groups, in order to complete the process.

Hospitals and medical practices, on the other hand, can provide significant cost-cutting opportunities by encouraging efficiency in the healthcare supply chain.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were made

- 1) Health care organizations should always build a long-term connection with their suppliers, allowing for the free flow of information and ideas. Over time, this will result in a more streamlined, efficient supply chain, which could improve prices, customer service, and goal achievement.
- 2) Health care organizations should implement CRM systems that assist hospitals enhance their relationships with current customers, find new customers, and reclaim former consumers by increasing the quality of services provided to patients
- 3) Inter-departmental friction frequently emerges as a result of each department believing that they contribute more to the firm and work harder than others. This is often exacerbated by some bosses' seemingly arbitrary performance evaluations, but with better information exchange among staff, such tension will be reduced.

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